

Eurodoc Annual Report 2021/2022

Brussels, 10 June 2022

Edited by: Eurodoc Board for Eurodoc Administration 2021/2022

Foreword

Dear All,

Our Board was born in the midst of the pandemic: we've been the second Eurodoc Administration in history who never met in person, and during this term we experienced some "long covid" effects on our work and lives. Moreover, as Eurodoc was founded in 2002, we have been the first Eurodoc Administration in history to witness a war in Europe, and to face the urgent need to support our own members that are experiencing war in their own country. As Eurodoc turned 20 (we hosted an online 20th Anniversary celebration in early February), we felt the need for change.

Thanks to the work of the previous Administrations, Eurodoc is now a well known and respected stakeholder representing ECRs in Europe. During this term, our main challenge was to keep a good balance between the time invested in cooperation with partners and stakeholders, and the time devoted to the internal restructuring, aimed to equip the future Eurodoc Administrations with a more flexible and efficient internal structure. To change the internal structure of an organisation is always a challenging and delicate process: it required us more than a half of the time we invested in our Eurodoc activities. We are deeply grateful to all Administration members that contributed to this effort, each one with the utmost dedication and generosity.

The results of our efforts will emerge in the next year, when the changes will become operative. We pass our work on to the next Eurodoc Administration, that will implement these innovations, and will need to devise further adjustments.

During this year, the main challenge we experienced was the tiredness faced by all our members: two years of COVID-19 pandemic brought an extraordinary burden on individuals' private and working lives. We had a high number of resignations from Administration positions, which further slowed down Eurodoc activities. After February 24th, the psychological and material difficulties of our Ukrainian colleagues dramatically increased, as the pressure felt by all of us.

However, we are proud to point out that we did our best to take care of one another, to support each other, and to continue to advocate for ECRs in Europe. Each volunteer contributed at their best: in this report, we tried to name everyone, even for the smallest contribution.

In this regard, a special mention is for our National Associations, for the increased support they offered to Eurodoc. We conducted five internal meetings with our National Associations' delegates: we discussed internal management issues, advocacy contents and concerns. Our stance towards the invasion of Ukraine was discussed in detail with great objectivity, even under the collective shock, and was unanimously approved. The dedication showed and the great effort exerted in this extraordinary situation showed once again the power of thinking and acting together.

We can say it out loud: We are Eurodoc!

In this report, we'll provide an overview of the many activities performed during this year. To make it readable, we kept the report short, but we attached a number of reports from our working groups and officers, in order to provide more details on specific topics to be consulted at need.

This term is ending, but Eurodoc's activities are just at a new starting point. We are looking forward to meet all of you, in person or online, at the AGM 2022.

See you in Vilnius!

Eurodoc Administration Board members

Agnieszka Żyra, Sara Pilia, Danila Rijavec, Mariana Hankova,
Oleksandr Berezko, Pil Maria Saugmann and Sebastian Dahle

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1. Eurodoc objectives

Eurodoc shall pursue the following objectives according our [statute](#), [mission and vision](#):

- (a) **To represent** doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level in matters of education, research and professional development of their careers.
- (b) **To advance** the quality of doctoral programmes and the standards of research activity in Europe.
- (c) **To promote** the circulation of information on issues regarding young researchers, **organize** events, **take part** in debates, and **assist** in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.
- (d) **To establish** and **promote** cooperation between national associations representing doctoral candidates and junior researchers within Europe. Eurodoc shall not interfere with the competences of its member organisations in respect of all national matters and issues.

2. Eurodoc Members & Observers

National Associations (NAs)

Austria (Doktorat.at - OH), Belgium (Focus Research and PhD Society Leuven), Croatia (MLAZ), Czech Republic (SK RVŠ), Denmark (PAND), Finland (FUURT), France (CJC), Germany (THESIS), Hungary (DOSZ), Ireland (IFUT and USI), Italy (ADI), Latvia (LJZA), Lithuania (LSYR), Luxembourg (LuxDoc), Netherlands (PNN), Norway (SiN), Poland (KRD), Portugal (ABIC), Romania (ANOSR), Slovakia (ADS), Slovenia (YAS), Spain (FJI-Precarios), Sweden (SNPA and SFS/SFSDK), Switzerland (actionuni), Ukraine (RMU), and Azerbaijan (AYSPMU)

Observers

Individuals: Turkey, Bosnia Herzegovina

Organisations: Romania (Ro-Doc), Georgia (YSDCG)

Fig. 1 Eurodoc on a map

3. Eurodoc Administration Members

The Eurodoc administration consists of the Administrative board, Secretariat and Advisory board members.

Administrative Board

The Administrative Board is Eurodoc's regular executive body who shall represent, lead and administer Eurodoc's daily activities, and also follow the decisions adopted by the General Meeting.

<i>Position</i>	<i>Person</i>	<i>Association</i>
President	Agnieszka Żyra	Poland/KRD
Vice-President	Sara Pilia	Italy/ADI
Treasurer	Danila Rijavec	Slovenia/YAS
Secretary	Mariana Hanková	Czech Republic/SKRVŠ
General Board Member	Oleksandr Berezko	Ukraine/RMU
General Board Member	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
General Board Member	Sebastian Dahle	Slovenia/YAS

Secretariat

Secretariat members are part of the administration who help to carry on the Eurodoc annual goals, coordinated by the Administrative Board.

<i>Position</i>	<i>Person</i>	<i>Association</i>
Secretariat Coordinator	Bikal Ghimire (resignation)	Norway/SiN
External Communication Coordinator	Haneen Atallah (resignation)	Hungary/DOSz
Newsletter Coordinators	Constance Musseau (resignation) followed by Giulia Malaguarnera	Sweden/SNPA/ Italy/ADI
Language Officer	Sean Bisset	Sweden/SNPA
Webmaster	Oleksandr Berezko	Ukraine/RMU
CoE Officer	Beata Zwierzyńska	Poland/KRD
Skills Officer	Nicola Dengo	Italy/ADI
BFUG Officer	Iryna Hubeladze	Ukraine/RMU

Social Media Officer	Beata Zwierzyńska (resignation)	Poland/KRD
Social Media Officer	Francesco Consiglio (resignation)	Spain/FJI-precarios
EOSC Officer	Emanuele Storti	Italy/ADI
WG Doctoral Training Coordinator	Liv Teresa Muth (resignation)	Belgium/PhD Society
WG Equality Coordinator	Aziz Ben Miled	Germany/Thesis
WG Employment & Career Development Coordinator	Patrik Švančara	Czech Republic/SKRVŠ
WG Mental Health Coordinator	Mathias Schroijen	Belgium/OR
	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
WG Interdisciplinarity	Katarzyna Turoń	Poland/KRD
WG Mobility Coordinator	Danila Rijavec	Slovenia/YAS
WG Open Science Coordinators	Maja Dolinar	Slovenia/YAS
	Irina-Mihaela Dumitru	Sweden/ SFS-DK
WG Policy Research Coordinator	Katarzyna Turoń	Poland/KRD
WG Research Integrity Coordinator	Sebastian Dahle	Slovenia/YAS
	Déborah Chery	France/CJC
WG Democracy & Sustainability Coordinators	Véronique De Herde	Belgium/PhD Society

Advisory Board

The Advisory Board supports the Administrative board and other Eurodoc bodies with advice and facilitates the knowledge transfer between consecutive terms to assure the continuity of Eurodoc as an organisation.

Advisory board members for 2020/2021:

- Giulia Malaguarnera (Italy)
- Giuseppe Montalbano (Italy)
- Iryna Degtyareva (Ukraine)
- Margaux Kersschot (Belgium)
- Farouk Allouche (France)
- Mathias Schroijsen (Belgium)
- Eva Hnátková (Czech Republic)

4. Eurodoc Activities 2021/2022

In the Annual Report, we will mention the activities based on the Eurodoc Annual Goals, which were approved by AGM, which was held in Prague (Czech Republic) in 2021.

4.1 Developing awareness, policies and outputs on crucial topics for ECRs

As it was said in the foreword this year due to pandemic time as well unexpected circumstances caused by the war was very special. Due to that fact, unfortunately some of the planned events and priorities of the actions had to be changed.

Equality, Democracy and Sustainability

As a result of the Democracy & Sustainability Working Group's great efforts the Eurodoc [statement on Academic Freedom](#) was developed. This statement is nowadays crucial, in the big changes which can be observed in Europe. Eurodoc advocates to improve conditions among those as well as others on the topic of Academic Freedom. While the conditions of doctoral candidates and ECRs vary greatly across Europe, it must be recognised that they are professionals and as such, academia is their workplace - Academic Freedom concerns them as well.

In the *Rome Ministerial Communique* academic freedom is defined as

“freedom of academic staff and students to engage in research, teaching, learning and communication in and with society without interference nor fear of reprisal.”

From the perspective of Doctoral Candidates and ECRs, there are several levels that should be recognized as influencing the capacity of academic students and staff to experience and practice academic freedom. We advocate in this statement, which principles should be upheld at these different levels to ensure that Doctoral Candidates and Early Career Researchers, and more broadly academics, are in capacity to exert their academic freedom.

Eurodoc considers research as a crucial activity in the life of the whole society. For this reason, research is a complex process that benefits and involves a great number of different actors (the general public, international and national institutions, the private sector, academic institutions, individual researchers, etc). All of these actors have specific interests, have different rights and, in their own domain, should perform duties aimed at protecting academic freedom as a human right.

That is why in the statement Eurodoc underlined four levels of Academic Freedom understanding (society, governmental institutions and funders, independence of academia, academic freedom for the individual researchers).

Eurodoc has also produced a statement [on Academic Freedom in Slovenia](#). In the statement which was a response to the signals reported of the interference by the authorities in Academic Freedom in defunding of public established and independent universities protected by laws on Academic Freedom, implementation of national administrative measures that force an extreme reduction of students and/or researchers in study programs and research paths, general blocking on new employment for all state-funded higher education institutions and research-performing organizations (RPOs) as part of policies that seem to highly affect the public scientific sector and actively promoting among public opinion a biased image of the role of research, researchers and universities and higher education institutions, that lays the cultural background for concrete measures that actively affect Academic Freedom and the right to high quality education for all. We hope that our response as well as declaration of collaboration and monitoring with The Young Academy of Slovenia (Društvo Mlada akademija) influenced perceiving and understanding of Academic Freedom.

Mental Health

The Mental Health Working Group's great efforts succeeded in the development of the [Eurodoc statement on mental health](#), which was a very important issue for Eurodoc as an organization representing doctoral candidates and early career researchers - the group which unfortunately experiences many effects of mental health disorders. Eurodoc advocates to improve mental wellbeing among those as well as others in academia. While ECRs' working conditions vary greatly across Europe it must be recognised that they are professionals and as such academia is their workplace.

WHO's definition of a healthy workplace states that

“A healthy workplace is a place where everyone works together to achieve an agreed vision for the health and well-being of workers and the surrounding community. It provides all members of the workforce with physical, psychological, social and organizational conditions that protect and promote health and safety. It enables managers and workers to increase control over their own health and to improve it, and to become more energetic, positive and contented.”

To achieve that academia lives up to this definition of a healthy workplace for all ECRs we have identified the following 10 principles that must be met by the academic institutions and supported by national as well as European policy makers.

In the Equality Working Group a lot of actions were undertaken. During this term, Eurodoc gained good visibility within the COST Action “Voices” and established valuable contact through appointing our volunteer member Elettra Repetto as Stakeholders' Board Coordinator in addition to the potential involvement of Eurodoc in the COST action's surveys so that early career researchers' voices are heard in all stages of the research process. The members of the WG proposed to the Board the creation of a position of Gender Equality Officer, to focus on the Eurodoc administration organization and governance from a gender perspective and finalized the survey about Mobbing and Harassment. What is more Eurodoc contributed as well in “[Strategies for Sustainable Gender Equality](#)” project, increasing Gender Equality in Academia.

Open Science, Research Integrity and Research Assessment

In spring 2021, the European Commission launched '[Open Research Europe](#)' (ORE), an Open Access Publishing Platform for Horizon 2020 beneficiaries. ORE offers rapid publication of various article types without editorial bias. All articles benefit from transparent peer review and are published under an open license. The platform is a significant step towards Open Science in Europe. [Eurodoc](#), as an expert partner in the ORE

project, is ensuring that the voice of ECRs is heard. One of Eurodoc's tasks in supporting ORE is to help to develop a Sustainability Plan for the project. In particular, Eurodoc was obliged to organize two focus sessions from ECRs to inform the Sustainability Strategy through consultation with the Eurodoc community. The first focus session took place on November 25-27, 2021, online (due to pandemic situation), during the 10th International Youth Science Forum "[Litteris et Artibus](#)."

Conducted in a 2021 survey on "Publishing in Open Science" sought to gain new perspectives on OS knowledge and motivation for its adoption amongst researchers, using a range of different dimensions relevant to demographics and background. An international team of volunteers analysed and summarised the survey results, which were published in Open Access on 22 December 2021, as a [preprint on the F1000 Research platform](#) together with the [accompanying dataset](#).

The survey results suggest that the awareness and positive attitude regarding OS, specifically among ECRs, is high in Europe. However, there are significant career stage group differences in views and knowledge about OS. Generally, awareness and positive attitude tend to increase with increasing career seniority. Regarding European regions, there are three main groups sharing similar awareness levels and attitudes: researchers in Western Europe - the most informed group towards OS; researchers in northern, central, and southern Europe - a moderately informed group with some minor differences; and researchers in eastern Europe - the least informed group, whose opinions deviate the most. The analysis indicates an "evolution of needs and focus" regarding scientific publishing: researchers in most European regions are in different stages of transition from the competitive to collaborative levels, while researchers in eastern Europe are largely beginning their transition to the competitive level.

During the current term, Eurodoc conducted meetings with the partner organisation ICoRSA on research assessment, which led to Eurodoc's participation in three Horizon Europe proposals, one of which has meanwhile been granted (OPUS), whereas two are still under evaluation at the time of writing this report (ORRIOL, SECURE). Further activities on Research Assessment and Research Integrity included a [meeting](#) with the [Responsible Open Science in Europe \(ROSiE\)](#) project team, a [presentation](#) at the [PRIDE network's conference on assessing impact](#), a [Stakeholder meeting on Reforming Research Assessment](#), and the first [assembly meeting Towards an agreement on reforming research assessment](#).

Eurodoc is a full partner of the three-year (Jan 15 2021 - Jan 14 2023), EU-funded, and capacity-building Erasmus+ project in the field of higher education named "[Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia](#)" (OPTIMA). OPTIMA's priorities include engaging disadvantaged academic communities of displaced Ukrainian universities, focusing on climate change as well as inclusivity by means of modern information technologies. This project is coordinated by Lviv Polytechnic National University and is aimed at bringing modern and European Open Science practices to Ukraine. Eurodoc's role is to provide volunteers acting as Open Science experts for various project activities. The OPTIMA consortium also includes Vasyl Stus Donetsk National University, Sumy State University, Lutsk National Technical University, National Antarctic Scientific Center and the National Agency for Higher Education Quality Assurance. Project's diverse international partners are Graz University of Technology (Austria), Wrocław University of Science and Technology (Poland), University of Côte d'Azur (France), the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc, Belgium), Stichting eIFL.net (Netherlands). Associated partners: Council of Rectors of Displaced Universities, Centre for Innovation and Sustainability for International Development and Antiplagiati Ltd.

Unfortunately, due to the fact of the war in Ukraine some of the planned actions had to be modified, postponed and adjusted to the current situation in this country.

Eurodoc is also a full partner in the Open and Universal Science (OPUS) project, under HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-45, Cooperation for innovation and the exchange

of good practices. The OPUS project will develop coordination and support measures to reform the assessment of research and researchers at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) towards a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to practice Open Science. The term 'Open Science' refers to practices providing open access to research outputs, early and open sharing of research, participation in open peer-review, measures to ensure reproducibility of results, involving all stakeholders in co-creation. We henceforth in this proposal employ this interpretation of Open Science with a specific focus on reforming the research(er) assessment system to incentivise and reward researchers to take up these practices. OPUS employs a three-tiered approach to ensure representation and consensus building of key stakeholder groups in the Open Science ecosystem:

1. the large project consortium consists of researcher organisations, RPOs, RFOs, industry organisations, and experts in project management, public relations, and Open Science
2. a series of stakeholder engagement sessions will be held with the broader community to gather input and validate key project deliverables
3. an Advisory Board of key representatives will ensure expert oversight and links to the community.

Eurodoc particularly collaborates in the state of the art on Open Science incentives, metrics and indicators, as well as in drafting and disseminating policy recommendations.

Interdisciplinarity, Intersectoral and International mobility

Eurodoc believes that research and knowledge should not be restricted to a specific framework, either geographically or sectorally. For so, it strongly believes that interdisciplinarity along with intersectoral and international mobility is embedded in the wider doctoral training. Researchers are not typically provided with sufficient opportunity or knowledge on mobility options, which would otherwise enable them to think globally and boost their local research. Therefore, the Mobility working group (WG) provided an updated information on [mobility schemes and individual fellowships](#). As they are an important channel to facilitate mobility and contributing to career development among Early Career Researchers (ECR), we need to address the challenges and benefits of current mobility programs in different European countries and raise awareness of mobility's importance. Namely, fostering mobility enables wide and balanced circulation of talent. For many early career researchers, mobility may be the only way to gain access to research facilities required for innovation. Mobility gives researchers the opportunity to work with experts in their fields outside of their countries of origin and disciplines.

For most, the integration into multinational, multicultural environments typically leads to early scientific maturity and independence. Based on this, they contribute more research, more papers and more outputs. To raise the voice of the importance of this, Danila Rijavec on behalf of the Mobility WG joined the [EU - European University Foundation panel discussion](#) on implementing doctoral mobility, specifically on institutional, supervision-related and PhD project-related challenges to the implementation of PhD mobility and how to overcome them. Furthermore, there seem to be highly unbalanced mobility flows across Europe. For example, for each incoming student in Eastern Europe, there are at least two that go to Western Europe. Adding to this challenge, Danila Rijavec on behalf of the Mobility WG added to the [Yerun's panel](#) on Multiplier event "[How to improve doctoral training through joint programmes. Analysis of experiences in international collaboration](#)", MSCA Presidency Conference on "[Fostering Balanced Mobility Flows in Europe](#)" and [Elsevier's](#) webinar on "[Shaping European universities through means of collaboration – tracking the benefits of academic networks and alliances](#)".

4.2 Lobby for policy and/or cultural changes of profound importance to ECRs

Advocacy for Ukrainians ECRs

After Russia's invasion of Ukraine on February 29th, Eurodoc rapidly issued two documents to express our support to Ukrainian ECRs and people, and to request EU institutions action ([here](#) and [here](#)). It is worthy to point out that one of the statements was a joint statement with Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA). It has been the first time that Eurodoc faced the need to express itself on such an event, and a long discussion was needed to our National associations (NAs) to elaborate a responsible position from the ECRs perspective.

We then established an "Ukraine taskforce", that tried to organise the many ideas for support coming from our members, and the concrete needs expressed by our Ukrainian member RMU. The most relevant result of this effort was a [comprehensive analysis](#) of concrete needs of Ukrainians ECRs and of the support offered from other countries and research institutions. For this, we would like to thank our volunteers Sebastian Dahle (General Board member) and Hannah Schoch (Switzerland/ActionUni), that did the most part of this work.

The overall situation greatly changed after the first month of war and in the next years Ukrainian ECRs and Research system will face unprecedented challenges. Eurodoc should continue to periodically monitor the situation and advocate for the implementation of proper support to rebuild and restart research and academic work in Ukraine.

Scholars at Risk's Urgent appeal to European Governments and EU Institutions

Eurodoc was observing the terrible events unfolding in Afghanistan during the end of NATO's involvement in the region. Eurodoc believes that protecting academic freedom for present and future generations of scholars all over the world is crucial to shaping mutual understanding, contributing to scientific knowledge, and the advancement of society as a whole. From this point, on September 13, 2021 Eurodoc published a statement on the ["Scholars at Risk" appeal](#) to the European Governments and EU Institutions to act urgently for Afghanistan's scholars, researchers, and civil society actors. Eurodoc fully supported the appeal of higher education institutions, associations, networks, and leaders in the field of scholar protection, urging European governments and EU institutions to take immediate action to secure the lives and careers of Afghanistan's students, early career researchers, professionals as well as civil society actors.

4.3 Engagement of stakeholders/partners on Eurodoc's key topics

Conference of International NGOs of the Council of Europe

During this term Eurodoc was able to interact directly with the [Conference of INGOs](#) of the Council of Europe, on some different topics. This effort was supported by our CoE Officer Beata Zwierzynska, who had been elected as a Conference of INGOs Standing Committee member.

Academic freedom: we had a few meetings with the President of the Conference of INGOs on academic freedom, and stimulated the Conference to develop some awareness raising activities on academic freedom together with some of our National associations. However, these activities were put on hold after the invasion of Ukraine, when the Conference of INGOs switched its attention mostly to the unfolding events and related issues.

Gender Equality: Sara Pilia was elected Secretary of the Committee ["NGOs as advocates for gender equality and women's rights"](#) of the Conference of INGOs, and she shared some of the Eurodoc work on the topic with other NGOs. In this context, we started

building direct cooperation with some of these NGOs concerned with our same issues. We are currently discussing with them their involvement in two Eurodoc projects: one is the COST Action 'Voices' led by the Equality WG) and one is a future project linked with the implementation of Gender Equality Plan activities.

Education as a Human right: the Conference of INGOs is working on the establishment of a Education committee, in which Eurodoc added our concerns about academic freedom and research integrity. More work can be developed in the future, also thanks to the new Statement on academic freedom and the establishment of the Research and Society WG.

ISE - Initiative for Science Europe

Collaboration with ISE is important for Eurodoc, as it is an independent platform of European Learned Societies and Research Organizations involving researchers in the design and implementation of European science policies and advocating strong independent scientific advice in European policy making. Sebastian and Agnieszka participated in discussions during a live [Meeting on key issues for the future of European research in October 2021](#) in Brussels, three online meetings in [November](#), [January](#) and [May](#), as well as the [ISE General Assembly](#) in March 2022. Moreover, during the Widening Workshop: "A diagnosis of the situation in the EU" Eurodoc had the opportunity to [present](#) the perspective of Junior Researchers.

Science Europe

Eurodoc has a great opportunity to participate this year in the discussion about research culture, which is a very relevant topic. We were invited to participate in the [Science Europe High Level Workshop on ERA](#), which was the biggest event with important stakeholders. The High Level Workshop addressed the broad topic of research culture and focused on two key themes: research careers, and reward and incentive structures. Discussions began with an exploration of some core concepts of research cultures in Europe and how they are linked to the values at the foundation of research activity. During the panel session, Eurodoc President Agnieszka Żyra introduced several key concerns that should be considered as part of discussions around changing research cultures. Firstly, research precarity and the prevalence of temporary contracts creates stress as all early-career researchers consider their futures, including future job and income security. A study performed by EURODOC in 2020 highlighted some large inequalities and differences across Europe where, giving Open Science as an example, knowledge of and use of open science practices is common among early-career researchers in Northern and Western Europe, but much less so in Eastern Europe. Channels for the dissemination of research and science communication also varied greatly. These are important considerations when discussing research culture at a European level, and efforts must be made to reduce rather than exacerbate inequalities at an international level.

EUA-CDE

The EUA-CDE is the biggest European gathering of stakeholders engaged in doctoral education and their annual meeting attracts around 200 participants each year. During the period July 2021 - June 2021 Eurodoc has participated or will be participating in 3 events organized by EUA-CDE.

The Annual Meeting in 2021 was held online 13th-15th of September. The meeting addressed the key challenges facing doctoral education in the fallout of the Covid-19 crisis. Participants discussed topics such as collaboration in doctoral education, the skills needed and development of doctoral candidates, the importance of academic freedom and the impact of the pandemic on doctoral education globally (see attached programme). Eurodoc participated in the [2021 EUA-CDE Annual Meeting](#). Here Eurodoc were given the chance to [speak](#) in the plenary session "The role of academic freedom for early-career researchers".

On January 20th 2022 Eurodoc participated in the online EUA-CDE Focus Group Workshop "[Doctoral education in Europe: Where are we heading?](#)". Here several

brainstorming sessions were held throughout the day, focusing on the topics of digitalization, green transition and diversity. The event contributed to the development of a new EUA-CDE vision paper on the future of doctoral education in Europe which will be presented at the EUA-CDE Annual meeting 2022.

The EUA-CDE Annual meeting 2022 will be held from the 22nd-24th of June at Manchester University. The meeting will address several issues connected to the question of time during doctoral training. Eurodoc has been invited to participate in the plenary session "Preparing for a doctorate. What can be done?". The full program can be found [here](#).

European Commission

Eurodoc has participated in several events, meetings as well as consultations regarding Reforming Research Assessment. ERA introduced a procedure to have one representative from various stakeholders groups. Eurodoc has joined Marie Curie Alumni Association, Initiative for Science in Europe, association of ERC Grantees and EuroScience stakeholders group (as individual researchers and innovators, including at early and middle stages of their careers). As a result we had to point out one representative who will attend all the consultations and meetings on behalf of us. After a consultation and voting Prof. Renaud Jolivet was elected as a representative of our group, supported by Prof. Agnieszka Wykowska.

4.4 Increase visibility of Eurodoc to remain as a relevant stakeholder and partner

Eurodoc 20th Anniversary

On 2 February 2022 Eurodoc turned 20 years old. We have organized panel discussions with our Partners (EUA-CDE and MCAA) as well as former and current Eurodoc Presidents. During the [online event](#), we reflected on Eurodoc's activism in the previous years and tried to look into the future of the European Research Area and the role of Early Career Researchers (ECRs) in it. It was a wonderful experience for us to see how Eurodoc has grown and changed as an organization within previous years. What is more, after this event we are sure that once you join the Eurodoc family you are a member forever and this is the strength of this organization. #WeAreEurodoc

In this occasion the [Wikipedia page](#) of Eurodoc was updated.

Eurodoc Annual Conference

[Eurodoc Conference 2022](#) titled "Building a Bridge Between Research and Business" due to unexpected circumstances was held online on **18-19 May 2022**. The event was co-organized by the Lithuanian Society of Young Researchers. The conference will focused on overlapping fields in research and business and how to transfer knowledge and skill between these areas. The aim of the event was to bring together everyone who wants to add value for themselves, their careers, universities, companies, and ultimately, for their states. We believe in our smallest and their high added value. To address all the issues mentioned before we have divided the Eurodoc conference into [seven topics areas](#). We would like once again to thank the invited [speakers](#).

ISPAS Project

Eurodoc was an International Advisory Board Member in the [ISPAS project](#), which has already ended. Basing on the collaboration between academic and non-academic partners from Italy, Spain, Bulgaria, and Norway ISPAS' overall objective of the project was to develop a new joint curricula of PhD courses that will take place in both academic and non-academic surroundings to equip PhD candidates from the STEM Sciences, Medical Sciences, Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities with competences and skills in the areas of open innovation and open science to facilitate PhD candidates' employment after graduation in and outside of academia. Specific objectives were:

- Based on the publicly available Catalan PhD tracking survey, coordinate the development of a PhD tracking survey by adding parts on transferable skills' acquisition for the PhD candidates of the Medical Sciences, STEM sciences, Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities.
- To develop a course to provide PhD candidates with basic skills on how to open up the entire cycle of their research and how to tell and disseminate science means enabling career paths both inside and outside academia (Basic FAIR data management skills learnt through the courses are the first step towards data stewardship, a highly requested position in the EOSC environment).
- To develop a course that will allow PhD candidates to acquire strong interdisciplinary foundation for future work in the field of digital humanities, to exploit their knowledge for digital humanities services and marketable products meant for different kind of industries, and thus provide a bridge for transfer of knowledge between the PhD candidates of the Humanities and STEM PhD candidates.
- To develop an Educational Innovation course to provide the candidates with the skills to create and manage both continuously existing innovative educational structures and short-term extracurricular initiatives.
- To develop a PhD skills course on entrepreneurship to provide PhD candidates with the knowledge, competences, tools, and skills to enable them to start up their own company.
- To provide PhD candidates with the skills to retrieve biomedical data from most relevant freely accessible databases, self-archive research data, generate statistical reports using literate, reproducible data analysis, apply the FAIR principles to biomedical and clinical trial data, create a research data management plan, and understand the ethical and legal issues of data storage and sharing in biomedical and clinical research.
- Create an online openly available platform to publish information on PhD courses being developed for the curricula that will function four years after the end of the project.
- Create publicly available guidelines for the PhD skills courses so that other stakeholders in the sector can easily replicate our activities.

Eurodoc was asked for final comments on ISPAS 1st bulk of PhD courses curricula, which we [produced](#), as well [presented and explained](#) during the ISPAS Advisory Board Meeting.

COST Action [VOICES](#)

It is a project focused on gender-based violence in academia that was drafted with the initial support of Eurodoc, during term 2020-2021, within the partnership established with the [Community of Practice "Strategies for Sustainable Gender Equality"](#). It aims at studying and improving the life of early career researchers, by drafting policy suggestions, publishing papers detailing survey results and organizing summer schools on the topic of gender-based violence.

Eurodoc has been essential in this study since the beginning, as we represent a great number of early career researchers. Being Eurodoc the most important stakeholder in this study, the project's management committee has appointed our volunteer Elettra Repetto, from the Equality WG, as Stakeholders' Board Coordinator.

In general, Eurodoc from participating in this action, will benefit in terms of view of visibility, but also by helping better representing the challenges of ECRs and factually participating in advancing meaningful policies, avoiding study samples to be so small the results to be non generalizable and the suggested policies to be irrelevant to many.

Contribution in preparing SECURE and ORRIOL project proposals

Together with 15 other organizations, Eurodoc collaborated in the project proposal **Open Responsible Research and Innovation to further Learning (ORRIOL)** for the Horizon Europe call *Developing and piloting training on the practice of open and responsible research and innovation* (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-44), which was coordinated by PLOCAN and ICoRSA.

If granted, ORRIOL will develop novel exploitation and sustainability plans for the practical implementation of Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) training to all EU researchers. ORRIOL will consolidate the existing ORRI evidence from other programs and projects and use this base to develop training materials and modules. The large range of EU project partners in the project will provide a conduit for the ORRI training material, modules, and platforms. These materials and modules will be trialled on a significant number of researchers that the project will have access to via partner networks as well as pilot RPOs. The project will comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of the training conducted in the trail, on the basis of greater career prospects, improved research excellence and increased science communication.

ORRIOL will:

- (1) Consolidate, adapt, and curate existing training materials on ORRI under one umbrella of ORRIOL ecosystem enabling easy find and completion of training
- (2) Trial training through: Predefined learning courses and learning paths using adapted FOSTER training tools & Adaptable learning packages delivering specific skills using eDoer platform
- (3) Micro-credentials awarded for ORRI completed courses
- (4) Make it possible to automatically connect all obtained accreditations to a researcher's profile, by linking to a researcher's globally unique ORCID ID

Eurodoc further took part with 18 other organisations in the project proposal **Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE)**, coordinated by PLOCAN and ICoRSA, for the Horizon Europe call *Developing an effective ERA talent pipeline* (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-50).

The Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework (RCF) that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity. The RCF will recognise the research profession across sectors, provide a career development and progression structure for research careers, recognise both research and transferable skills and competences, facilitate intersectoral collaboration and mobility, and offer solutions to the precariousness of research careers in academia. SECURE will test aspects of the RCF and TTL models in trials in four RPOs, one RFO, and one recruitment agency. The trial organisations will first conduct a scoping exercise to map the RCF onto their existing policies and activities for research careers before developing integration plans on how the RCF could be adopted into their existing policies and activities. Due to the short duration of the project and window for trials, it is expected that only some aspects of the RCF and TTL models will be tested. The trial organisations will thus develop actions plans, selecting relevant aspects from the integration plans, to test and implement during the trials. SECURE will mainstream the RCF and TTL models through a series of policy briefs and a summit that explain key aspects of the RCF and TTL models to relevant organisations employing researchers. The RCF and TTL models will be further promoted through key partner organisations in the project targeting researchers, RPOs, and companies. The RCF and TTL models will lastly be promoted in the EURAXESS network including the many EURAXESS service centres, the newly established EURAXESS hubs, and through the ERA Talent Platform being developed.

The evaluation results for both project proposals are still pending at the time of writing of this report.

4.5 Improving a sustainable internal Eurodoc governance.

One of the goals the AGM 2021 entrusted to this Board was to improve the internal structure of an organization, which is always a challenging and delicate process.

The main aim of this restructuring was to make Eurodoc more sustainable for its members and individual volunteers. In fact, in the previous years Eurodoc has experienced a relevant growth in visibility and an expansion of the topics it needs to follow up on. To sustain this growth and allow more people to join Eurodoc, we needed to streamline workflows and rationalise Eurodoc's internal structure.

Moreover, all the recent long-lasting events such as pandemics and war have led us to recognise the need to make adjustments and changes for the Eurodoc Administration to be able to manage unforeseeable circumstances in the future while respecting its democratic procedures.

In order to achieve these aims, we worked

- A. to prepare proposals of Eurodoc statute changes;
- B. to improve the Eurodoc Annual Questionnaire structure and content;
- C. to rationalise the Secretariat and improve its flexibility;
- D. to increase the dialogue between Eurodoc Administration and the National associations while reducing the flow of emails.

Statute and internal regulation changes

The Administrative board of Eurodoc has during its term worked on putting forward changes for the statutes and internal regulations. Eurodoc as an organisation has evolved over the last 7 years. The changes that has been suggested by the board aims at updating the statutes and internal regulation such that they reflect the organization Eurodoc has grown into. The type of changes falls in four different categories.

1. Editorial changes:
2. Updating the description of the current organizations Eurodoc
3. Changes to the size of the Administrative board.
4. Eurodoc as an employer

Annual Questionnaire

Eurodoc has during the last many years conducted an annual questionnaire. In 2021/2022 the annual questionnaire has undergone significant changes. This has been done in order to ensure that the outcome of the AQ to a larger degree can be used by Eurodoc. The questionnaire provides the members of Eurodoc with the opportunity of voicing the opinions on what Eurodoc should focus on during the next term.

The structure of Secretariat

In the last years, the number of Working groups increased to 10, and the external communication sector was expanded, as the team of Officers appointed on specific projects. During the AGM 2021 were issued calls for interest for 20 different positions.

The coordination of this group of volunteers is appointed by a single person, in the role of Secretariat coordinator. In the previous 2 years, this role has proven to be very hard; this year the person elected in this role resigned a month after the election.

The Board, and especially Vice President Sara Pilia, who had been Secretariat coordinator 2020-2021, has supervised the Secretariat reorganisation work. Two Secretariat meetings have been held during the year: one to start the work, in September, and another one to analyse with Secretariat members what was working and what was not working (in March).

After gathering information by the Secretariat members, and building on previous experience, the Board approved a proposal of reorganisation of the Secretariat structure to be voted at the AGM.

Following this restructuring, the “Guide to Eurodoc positions” was updated accordingly, to encourage NAs and their members to join Eurodoc Administration for next year.

A good practice introduced this year was the template for an “Annual Report” from single Secretariat members, that might be consulted by internal members here.

Dialogue between the Eurodoc administration and the National associations

In order to increase the dialogue with the National associations and reduce the flow of emails, the Board members Sara Pilia, Pil Maria Saugmann and Sebastian Dahle, coordinated 5 meetings of 2 hours each with the NAs to discuss different topics as:

- common understanding of Academic Freedom and Research assessment, as a basis for the work to be developed during the term (September)
- Annual Questionnaire structure (November)
- Christmas Party - team building session (December)
- changes in the Eurodoc Statute and Internal regulations (February)
- Eurodoc position on Russian aggression of Ukraine (February)

Of note, the two meetings in February were held one after the other, on the 28th of February, as the first one was planned long before, and the second was urgently needed. That day, most of the NAs were able to send at least one delegate per meeting; some delegates endured a 4 hour meeting, with moving commitment. Board members joined both meetings taking turns in chairing and taking notes, in a great team effort. Some Secretariat and Advisory Board members joined the meeting on the invasion of Ukraine too.

All these meetings were carefully planned in advance in order to allow all the delegates to discuss all the needed points in two hours, balancing sustainability and respect of democratic procedures of consultation.

Eurodoc representatives contributed to many conferences, meetings and events. We tried to collect all of them in the [mission reports](#), [presentations](#), as well as in the table in the next chapter.

5. Eurodoc Representations and Missions in 2021/2022

Name of the Eurodoc representative	Event	Date	Place/form
Sara Pilia and Sebastian Dahle	Discussion on CoE strategy with INGOS	31 Aug 2021	online
Mariana Hanková	Workshop on future ERA governance	2 Sep 2021	Brussels (Belgium)
Agnieszka Żyra	European Commission	3 September 2021	online

Giulia Malaguarnera	“Knowledge Ecosystem[M1] ” focus group	13 September 2021	online
Agnieszka Żyra	EUA-CDE Annual Meeting - presentation	13 September 2021	online
Pil Maria Saugmann Liv Teresa Muth		13-15 Sep 2021	Online
Nicola Dengo		14-15 Sep 2021	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	EC - University Alliance/ Stakeholder meeting on digitalization	14 Sep 2021	online
Agnieszka Żyra	EURECA-PRO WEEK	5 Oct 2021	Silesian University of Technology, Poland, online
Sara Pilia	CINGO Autumn Session	5-6 October	online
Sara Pilia/Beata?	CDPPE Plenary	13-15 October	online
Sara Pilia	CoP Strategies meeting	19 October	online
Sebastian Dahle	ISE: Meeting on key issues for the future of European research	19 October	Brussels, Belgium
Sara Pilia	CoP Strategies meeting	28 Oct 2021	online
Sara Pilia, Olek, Iryna	Youth Forum Ukraine	29 Oct 2021	online
Sebastian Dahle	ISE Members' meeting	19 Nov 2021	online
Agnieszka Żyra	Widening Participation Workshop	22 Nov 2021	online
Beata Zwierzyńska, Iryna Degtyarova, Sara Pilia	5th ETINED Plenary meeting	23 Nov 2021	Strasbourg, France, online

Agnieszka Żyra	High Level Workshop on ERA	24 Nov 2021	Luxembourg
Olek/Giulia/Aga	ORE conference	26 Nov 2021	
Patrik Švančara	Horizon Europe call with the EUF connected to PhD Hub and DocEnhance	30 Nov 2021	online
Olek	Horizon Europe Launch Day in Ukraine	3 Dec 2021	online
Sebastian Dahle	EC Stakeholder meeting on Reforming Research Assessment	8 Dec 2021	online
Sebastian Dahle, Iryna Degtyarova, Deborah Chery	Meeting with ROSiE project team – bilateral discussions	16 Dec 2021	online
Agnieszka Żyra	UNICA Doctoral Education Webinar: “The impact of international experience in the academic careers of Doctoral candidates”, https://www.unica-network.eu/ event/unica-doctoral-education -1stwebinar/	18 Jan 2022	online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Liv Teresa Muth	EUA-CDE Focus Group Workshop “ Doctoral education in Europe: Where are we heading? ”	20 Jan 2022	online
Sebastian Dahle	ISE: Meeting on the Future of European research	31 Jan 2022	online
Sebastian Dahle, Noémie Aubert Bonn	1st assembly meeting: Towards an agreement on reforming research assessment	3 March 2022	online
Agnieszka Żyra	MCAA 2021 award Jury meeting – member of Jury	11 March 2022	online
Sebastian Dahle, Patrik Švančara	Consultation meeting on the ERA Policy Agenda – Action 4 "Research Careers"	14 March 2022	online

Agnieszka Żyra, Sebastian Dahle	ISE general assembly	18 March 2022	online
Agnieszka Żyra	MCAA Annual Conference and General Assembly	26-27 March 2022	online
Sebastian Dahle, Mariana Hanková	The 4th Annual PRIDE Conference: Societal Impact in Doctoral Education: How do we support, realise and measure?	5-6 May 2022	Prague, Czechia
Sebastian Dahle	ISE meeting	17 May 2022	online
Agnieszka Żyra, Sara Pilia	"GET fit FOR YOUR FUTURE - The FIT FORTHEM online boot camp for Early Career Researchers"	1 June 2022	online

6. Eurodoc External Communication

Website

The Eurodoc website during the reporting period (Jul 15, 2021 – June 10, 2022) gained comparable popularity to the previous period. In total, it received around 29K users and around 60K pageviews (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Eurodoc website popularity (print screen from Google Analytics)

The most common website users' age group was people between 25 and 34 years of age (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Age of Eurodoc website audience (print screen from Google Analytics)

Most website visitors came from: USA (14.63%), UK (12.68%), China (5.22%), Germany (4.35%), Italy (4.17%), France (4.13%), Netherlands (3.16%), Spain (2.89%), India (2.68%), and Poland (2.28%). Small numbers of people from a large number of other countries then formed a “[long tail](#)” of 43.8% of visitors.

Social Media

Our followership grew on social media from July 2021 to June 2022.

- **Facebook** page followers grew from 6 613 to 6 911 (+4.5%); there were 35 new posts, the account audience was 39 312 users, it received 1 150 likes, and 186 shares.
- **Twitter** followers grew from 5 536 to 6 072 (+9.7%); there were 350 new tweets/retweets.
- **LinkedIn** followers grew from 2 283 to 2 824 (+23.7%); there were 34 new posts, the account got 1 460 page views and 687 unique visitors.
- The **YouTube** account grew from 92 to 120 subscribers (+30%); there were 9 new videos, the account received 1 500 views and 99.6 hours of watch time.

Newsletters

We are aware of the fact that the Eurodoc Newsletter is an important part of presenting Eurodoc activities, bringing together stakeholders and sharing information about events which might be interesting for ECRs. With the help of Giulia Malaguarnera - Eurodoc Advisory Board Member, we were able to prepare a Newsletter till February. Unfortunately without a Newsletter coordinator it was impossible for us to conduct it longer, which we really regret.

7. Special Thanks from the President

I had a great pleasure to work and act this year as Eurodoc president. I am very happy that I had a chance to work with wonderful Board and Administration members. During our term we could also always count on the advice from Advisory Board Members, which we really appreciate. Eurodoc are people, great people, who I had a chance to get to know better as well as to learn a lot from them, which I am grateful for.

The year that comes to a close was really hard because of pandemic time, as well as due to the war which started in the middle of Europe and also because of the fact that we had to handle the problem of Administration members leaving during the year. Unfortunately, we realized that Eurodoc needs to be ready for extraordinary situations which may occur in the near future. That is why we focused this year on the internal changes which in our opinion might help in the future sustainable growth and development of the Eurodoc as an organization. All our proposals for changes of the Secretariat and Working groups structure, as well as Eurodoc Statute and Internal Regulations can be found in the documents we have prepared.

I want to strongly thank all of you who contributed to NAs meetings, consulted Eurodoc statements, as well as took part in special events, who devoted time for Eurodoc actions. It was a pleasure to see your commitment in the created Ukrainien Task Force, as well as donations and financial support to our Ukrainien NA. These actions showed that we are Eurodoc, a great team, and that we can always count on each other.

I want to thank all the Working Group Coordinators and Eurodoc Officers, without you there would be no Eurodoc. Similarly, I want to thank the Advisory Board of Eurodoc, for the work you have all done for Eurodoc today and in the past.

My warmest thanks for the fantastic cooperation go to Sara, Danila, Mariana, Pil, Sebastian and Oleksandr - Eurodoc Administrative Board Members. I haven't had the chance to meet you in person, but after a year of working with you I feel like we've known each other for a long time. And this is a fantastic indicator that we have managed to create a team. I hope that you feel the same!

It is impossible to mention by name all the people I would like to thank for their help, support and good advice, but I hope you know how much I appreciate your help!

I would like to wish the future Eurodoc Administrative Board success, which will lead to the further development of Eurodoc.

Best wishes,
Agnieszka Żyra
Eurodoc President 2021/2022